

Bioactivity of autotrophic and mixotrophic *Tetraselmis chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) extracts against H₂O₂-mediated stress in A549 cells.

Thomas Conlon^{a,*}, Helen Herbert^{a,b}, Eva Campion^b, Nicolas Touzet^a

^a Centre for Environmental Research Innovation and Sustainability (CERIS), Atlantic Technological University Sligo, Sligo, Ireland

^b Department of Life Science, Faculty of Science, Atlantic Technological University Sligo, Sligo, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

The trophic regime experienced by microalgae can influence their accumulation of antioxidant products such as phenolic compounds. This study investigated the antioxidant capacity and bioactivity of Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS) extracts from the marine chlorophyte *Tetraselmis chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) cultivated under autotrophic and mixotrophic regimes. Compared to autotrophic conditions, mixotrophic cultivation significantly increased biomass yield (6.0-fold), soluble protein yield (5.7-fold) and Trolox-equivalent antioxidant capacity as measured by Folin-Ciocalteu (6.8-fold), DPPH (42.2-fold) and ABTS (15.3-fold) assays. For bioactivity, DPBS extracts (normalised by soluble protein content) were examined for their protective effects against hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂)-mediated apoptosis in pulmonary carcinoma epithelial cells (A549). Both autotrophic and mixotrophic-derived extracts exhibited a dose-dependent response in H₂O₂-stressed A549 cells, with significant cytoprotection observed at higher concentrations (200 µg soluble protein mL⁻¹), while lower concentrations were insufficient to mitigate oxidative damage and were associated with reduced cell viability. These effects involved modulation of apoptosis-related mRNA expression (*BCL2* and *BAX*). The bioactive content of both autotrophic and mixotrophic-derived extracts exhibited similar biological activity with properties that may be beneficial in pulmonary pharmacology. Importantly, mixotrophy significantly upregulated the bioactive content of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) compared to obligate autotrophy (34.2-fold accounting for soluble protein yield and biomass generation).

1. Introduction

Oxidative stress is central to the pathogenesis of acute lung injury and inflammatory lung diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and coronavirus disease (COVID-19) [1,2]. Preclinical investigations have shown that exogenous antioxidants can alleviate oxidant-mediated lung damage by scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) and restoring redox balance disrupted by chronic inflammation [2,3]. Consequently, the identification of novel, safe and effective antioxidants is a key priority in pulmonary pharmacology [3]. Microalgae constitute a renewable, sustainable source of antioxidants such as phenolic compounds, flavanols, tocopherols, carotenoids, phycobiliproteins, mycosporine-like amino acids, glutathione and vitamins [4–6]. In this context, the chlorophyte *Tetraselmis* genus is known to synthesise potent antioxidants, such as the polyphenol quercetin and the water-soluble vitamin ascorbic acid (vitamin C) [7,8]. For

example, Cardoso *et al.* [7] reported that quercetin and caffeic acid were the primary polyphenolic constituents in aqueous extracts of *Tetraselmis* sp. IMP3. In this regard, both quercetin and derivatives of caffeic acid have been shown to exhibit antifibrotic and anti-inflammatory properties that alleviate pulmonary fibrosis *in vivo* [9,10]. A key factor influencing the accumulation of antioxidant metabolites in microalgae is the trophic regime, which refers to the mode of nutrient acquisition (e.g., autotrophy, heterotrophy, and mixotrophy) [11]. Autotrophic microalgae rely solely on light and inorganic carbon (e.g., CO₂) for energy and growth, while heterotrophic organisms utilise organic carbon sources in the absence of light. Mixotrophy integrates both strategies, enabling microalgae to photosynthesise while also metabolising external organic carbon sources [12]. This flexible metabolic capacity has been shown to significantly enhance biomass yield and promote the accumulation of antioxidant and bioactive compounds in several microalgal species including *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Spirulina (Arthrospira)*

* Correspondence to: Centre for Environmental Research Innovation and Sustainability (CERIS), Atlantic Technological University Sligo, Ash Ln, Ballytivnan, Sligo F91 YW50, Ireland.

E-mail address: thomas.conlon@research.atu.ie (T. Conlon).

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platensis [5,11,13].

In this context, *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) is a facultative mixotroph, capable of flexible resource acquisition [11,14]. Previous work has demonstrated that mixotrophic cultivation increases the antioxidant content of ethanolic extracts from this strain compared to obligate photoautotrophy [11]. Furthermore, *Tetraselmis*-derived extracts have demonstrated promising bioactivity *in vitro*, particularly in models relevant to oxidative stress and inflammation. For instance, diethyl ether extracts from *Tetraselmis* species have been shown to promote recovery in hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂)-stressed A549 human lung epithelial cells by enhancing cell viability and reducing intracellular ROS levels [15]. Similarly, ethanolic extracts of *Tetraselmis suecica* (CCMP 906) have been reported to attenuate oxidative damage in A549 cells, further supporting the cytoprotective potential of this genus [16]. In addition to antioxidant activity, *Tetraselmis*-derived extracts exhibit anti-inflammatory properties, as evidenced by reduced nitric oxide (NO) production and downregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) in lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-stimulated RAW264.7 macrophages [17]. These immunomodulatory effects appear to be mediated through inhibition of key signaling pathways, including the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) and nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) cascades [17]. Collectively, these studies highlight the potential of *Tetraselmis* species as a source of multifunctional bioactive compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Their ability to modulate oxidative stress and inflammatory signaling pathways suggests relevance for therapeutic applications in the management of oxidative stress-related pulmonary diseases.

Despite the known antioxidant potential of *Tetraselmis* species, relatively few studies have evaluated whether trophic-induced increases in antioxidant content translate into functional cytoprotective effects in human cell models. Moreover, prior research has primarily focused on organic solvent extracts, which may not be optimal for applications requiring biocompatible, aqueous-based delivery. To address this gap, this study used freeze-thaw-assisted extraction in Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS), a physiologically compatible medium, to obtain water-soluble antioxidant fractions from *T. chuii* cultivated under autotrophic and mixotrophic conditions. Antioxidant capacity was evaluated using Trolox-equivalent Folin-Ciocalteu, DPPH, and ABTS assays, while bioactivity was assessed through cell viability, dose-response, and apoptosis-related gene expression (*BAX*, *BCL2*) in H₂O₂-stressed A549 pulmonary epithelial cells. This dual approach allowed for the assessment of both chemical antioxidant potential and functional cellular outcomes. To ensure consistent exposure across treatments in the bioactivity assays, extract dosing was standardised based on soluble protein content, a common and reproducible metric for aqueous extracts that serves as a quantifiable and reproducible marker of the soluble, biologically relevant extract fraction including co-extracted phenolics, flavonoids, peptides, and other small molecules. The primary motivation was to determine whether mixotrophic cultivation enhances not just antioxidant content, but also cytoprotective activity in a physiologically relevant *in vitro* model. Given the central role of oxidative stress in pulmonary disease and the bioactivity of *Tetraselmis*-derived compounds, this study aims to bridge the gap between biochemical antioxidant potential and functional cellular outcomes. By linking trophic-induced biochemical changes to cytoprotective effects *in vitro*, this study provides valuable insight into the therapeutic potential of *T. chuii* as a natural antioxidant source for respiratory health and broader applications in pharmaceuticals and cosmetics targeting oxidative stress.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Microalgal culture

Tetraselmis chuii (Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa strain 66/21B) was cultured at 15 \pm 1 °C using a light intensity of 85 μ mol photons

m⁻² s⁻¹ with light:dark cycles of 14:10 hours in f/2 (-Si) medium enriched seawater. Photon flux density was determined using a model QLS2101 radiometer (Biospherical Instruments Inc. San Diego, CA, USA). Axenic cultures were prepared for adaptation to mixotrophic cultivation by modification of the protocol established by Azma *et al.* [18]. As such, the cultures were subjected to 300 \times g centrifugation at ambient temperature (20–25 °C) for 10 minutes (Eppendorf Centrifuge 5702, Eppendorf SE, Hamburg, Germany). The supernatant was discarded and the cell pellet was resuspended in a fresh f/2 (-Si) medium for two further rounds of centrifugation. An antibiotic treatment of vancomycin (5 mg L⁻¹) and neomycin (10 mg L⁻¹) was then used to maintain axenicity during mixotrophic cultivation.

2.2. Microalgal autotrophic and mixotrophic cultivation

Triplicate f/2 (-Si) autotrophic and f/2 (-Si) mixotrophic cultures (1 mg wet biomass mL⁻¹) were prepared in 100 mL sterile round bottom test tubes in which 10 mL of axenic alga stock (6 mg wet biomass mL⁻¹) was inoculated in 50 mL of medium. The cultures were cultivated at 15 \pm 3 °C with light: dark cycles of 14:10 hours (80 \pm 5 μ mol photons m⁻² s⁻¹) for a 28-day batch regime. Cultures were homogenised twice-weekly at 1500 rpm for 10 seconds using a Stuart SA8 vortex mixer (Bibby Sterilin Ltd., Staffordshire, UK). The f/2 (-Si) medium was prepared according to the method of Guillard [19] with the following composition: macronutrients were NaNO₃ (7.5 \times 10⁻² g L⁻¹), NaH₂PO₄·H₂O (5 \times 10⁻³ g L⁻¹); micronutrients were FeCl₃·6H₂O (3.15 \times 10⁻³ g L⁻¹); Na₂EDTA·2H₂O (4.36 \times 10⁻³ g L⁻¹), MnCl₂·4H₂O (1.8 \times 10⁻⁴ g L⁻¹), ZnSO₄·7H₂O (2.2 \times 10⁻⁵ g L⁻¹), CoCl₂·6H₂O (1 \times 10⁻⁵ g L⁻¹), CuSO₄·5H₂O (9.8 \times 10⁻⁶ g L⁻¹), Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O (6.3 \times 10⁻⁶ g L⁻¹); vitamins included Thiamine HCl (1 \times 10⁻⁴ g L⁻¹), Biotin (5 \times 10⁻⁷ g L⁻¹), and Cyanocobalamin (5 \times 10⁻⁷ g L⁻¹). The mixotrophic medium was composed of f/2 (-Si) with additions of peptone (9 g L⁻¹), glucose (6 g L⁻¹), yeast extract (4.5 g L⁻¹), meat extract (3 g L⁻¹), vancomycin (5 mg L⁻¹) and neomycin (10 mg L⁻¹) [18,20]. These conditions followed those described in Conlon *et al.* [11].

2.3. Microalgal growth analysis and biomass harvesting

T. chuii (CCAP 66/21B) growth was monitored twice-weekly by optical density analysis. Specifically, the absorbance of 300 μ L of homogenised culture was determined at λ 600 nm using a FLUOstar OMEGA microplate reader (BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany) [21].

Specific growth rates (μ , day⁻¹) were calculated as follows:

$$\mu = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{N_2}{N_1}\right)}{\delta t}$$

Where μ is the specific growth rate, N_1 is the cell density at time 1, N_2 is the cell density at time 2, and δt is the length of the time in days between N_1 and N_2 .

At day 28 of cultivation, all cultures were subjected to 300 \times g centrifugation at ambient temperature for 10 minutes. The biomass pellet was desalted using 0.5 M ammonium formate. Centrifugation was repeated at 1000 \times g for 5 minutes at ambient temperature (Labnet, prism microcentrifuge, Labnet International Inc., Woodbridge, NJ, USA). The biomass pellet was then lyophilized, weighed and stored at -20 °C prior to analysis.

2.4. Microalgal DPBS extract preparation

2.4.1. Extract preparation for biochemical analysis

Extraction was carried out by a modification of the procedure of McGee *et al.* [22]. As such, approximately 15 micro-glass beads and 1 mL of sterile DPBS (without calcium and magnesium) were added to 2.5 mg of freeze-dried biomass ($n = 3$). The samples were vortexed for

30 seconds at 3000 rpm (FB15012 Topmix, Fisher Scientific GmbH, Schwerte, Germany). The samples were then ground for 60 seconds at 4 m s^{-1} (FastPrep FP120, Qbiogene Inc., Heidelberg, Germany). After a freeze-thaw cycle, centrifugation was carried out at $8000 \times g$ for 5 minutes at ambient temperature. The supernatants were collected for immediate analysis of soluble protein and antioxidant content, as reported in 3.2.

2.4.2. Extract preparation for cell-based assays

For cell-based experiments, biomass quantities were adjusted to yield comparable soluble protein content across conditions (20 mg for autotrophic-derived and 5 mg for mixotrophic-derived freeze-dried biomass). The extraction procedure was identical to that described in 2.4.1. Following extraction, the soluble protein content of each extract was quantified, and the extracts were subsequently diluted in DPBS to reach final working concentrations ranging from 12.5 to 200 μg soluble protein mL^{-1} . Extract doses applied in the cell-based assays were normalised to soluble protein content (BSA equivalent), to ensure consistent delivery of extractable, water-soluble bioactive material across treatments. This approach was chosen to account for the complexity of the DPBS-based extracts, which contain not only proteins but also co-extracted phenolics, peptides, and other small water-soluble compounds. To validate the use of protein-normalised dosing, a correlation analysis was performed between soluble protein concentration and A549 cell viability across the tested dose range (6.25–200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) under H_2O_2 -induced oxidative stress. Pearson correlation coefficients and R^2 values were calculated to assess the strength of association, and the resulting scatter plots are presented in [Supplementary Fig. S1](#).

2.5. Soluble protein content of DPBS extracts

The soluble protein content of extracts was determined by the colorimetric detection of bicinchoninic acid (Pierce BCA kit). Specifically, 25 μL of DPBS microalgal extract was added to 200 μL of reaction mixture. Following incubation in the dark for 30 minutes at 37°C , absorbance was measured at λ 562 nm. A bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard curve was used for soluble protein BSA-equivalent quantification ($n = 10$, 25–2000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.997$, $y = 0.0007x + 0.2082$).

2.6. Antioxidant capacity of DPBS extracts

2.6.1. Folin-Ciocalteu assay

The antioxidant activity in the microalgae extracts was measured using the Folin-Ciocalteu assay, with results expressed as Trolox equivalents. This assay quantifies the overall antioxidant activity of the extracts, reflecting the combined effects of phenolics and other antioxidants present. Specifically, 100 μL of DPBS extract obtained from 2.5 mg of freeze-dried biomass was added to 500 μL of 1:10 diluted Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Merk KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). After 5 minutes, 400 μL of saturated sodium carbonate (37.5 g L^{-1}) was added and the mixture was incubated in the dark for 4 hours at ambient temperature. Absorbance was measured at λ 760 nm (Jenway 6305 UV/Visible spectrophotometer, Bibby Sterilin Ltd., Staffordshire, UK). The antioxidant activity was quantified by comparing the extract's response to a standard curve of Trolox ($n = 8$, 100–1500 μM , $R^2 = 0.999$, $y = 0.0005 + 0.0011$). Trolox is a known antioxidant and was used to measure the overall antioxidant potential of the extracts, reflecting a broad range of antioxidant compounds, including phenolics, flavonoids, carotenoids, and other bioactive compounds.

2.6.2. Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC) assay

For the TEAC Assay, a 2,2'-azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) radical cation solution (ABTS+) was prepared by the reaction of 7 mM ABTS with 2.45 mM potassium persulfate [23]. Following 24-hour incubation in the dark at 4°C , the ABTS+ solution was diluted with ethanol (50 % v/v) to an absorbance of 0.70 ± 0.05 at λ 734 nm.

For analysis, 100 μL of DPBS extract obtained from 2.5 mg of freeze-dried biomass was added to 900 μL of diluted ABTS+ solution and incubated in the dark for 15 minutes at ambient temperature. Absorbance was then measured at λ 734 nm. Trolox equivalents were quantified using a trolox standard curve ($n = 8$, 0.5–100 μM , $R^2 = 0.990$, $y = -0.0015x + 0.1788$).

2.6.3. Free radical scavenging assay (DPPH)

A 0.25 mM solution of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was diluted with ethanol (50 % v/v) to an absorbance of 0.70 ± 0.05 at λ 515 nm. The diluted DPPH (900 μL) was then mixed with DPBS extract (100 μL) obtained from 2.5 mg of freeze-dried biomass. Following incubation in the dark for 30 minutes at ambient temperature, the absorbance was measured at λ 515 nm. To account for potential interference from residual photosynthetic pigments absorbing at λ 515 nm, blank corrections were performed by measuring the absorbance of each extract in ethanol (without DPPH) at the same wavelength. These values were subtracted from the corresponding DPPH reaction absorbance to ensure that the radical scavenging activity reflected only the DPPH reduction. This correction was applied consistently across all samples and standards. Trolox equivalents were quantified using a trolox standard curve ($n = 8$, 0.5–200 μM , $R^2 = 0.991$, $y = -0.0005x + 0.2468$).

2.7. Human alveolar epithelial cell culture

A549 cells (human lung adenocarcinoma cell line) were maintained in Ham's F12 medium supplemented with 10 % v/v fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1 % w/v penicillin-streptomycin at 37°C , 5 % CO_2 . Cells were sub-cultured every two days, and exponential phase cells were used in all experiments. Cell viability and concentration were determined using the trypan blue exclusion assay as described in Cooper *et al.* [24]. For the experiments, A549 cells (100 μL , 3×10^4 cells mL^{-1}) were seeded in 96-well plates and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C , 5 % CO_2 . Cells were then treated with microalgal DPBS extract (6.25–200 μg soluble protein mL^{-1}) for 24 hours or pre-exposed to the extract for 1 hour, followed by co-treatment with H_2O_2 (0.45 mM) for a total cumulative treatment of 24 hours. Doxorubicin (2.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was used as a positive control for cytotoxicity. DPBS and non-treated cells were included as vehicle and negative controls, respectively.

2.8. Cell viability assay

Following treatments, cell viability was determined using the Promega CellTiter 96 Aqueous One Solution Cell Proliferation (MTS) assay according to the manufacturer's instructions. Absorbance was measured at λ 490 nm. Absorbance values were adjusted to compensate for background contribution and normalised to the DPBS vehicle control. Percentage viability was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Viability} = \left[\frac{\text{Experimental viability}}{\text{Negative control viability}} \right] \times 100.$$

Values were expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments.

2.9. Cytotoxicity assay

Following treatments, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) values were determined using the LDH-Cytotoxicity Assay Kit II (Abnova) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 100 μL of LDH reaction mixture was added to 10 μL of clear medium solution for all treatment groups. After incubation for 30 minutes at ambient temperature, absorbance values were measured at λ 485 nm. Absorbance values were adjusted to compensate for background contribution and normalised to the DPBS vehicle control. The percentage cytotoxicity was calculated as follows:

% Cytotoxicity = [Experimental LDH release/Maximum LDH release] × 100.

Values were expressed as mean ± SD of three independent experiments.

2.10. Acridine orange staining and epi-fluorescence

Acridine orange staining was used to assess the cytoprotective effects of the microalgal DPBS extracts against H₂O₂-induced apoptosis as described by Herbert *et al.* [25]. Following treatments, the medium was carefully discarded and the cells were washed twice with PBS. The cells were then stained with 100 µL of acridine orange/PBS solution (100 µg mL⁻¹) for 10 minutes at ambient temperature, followed by observation using red (λ 560 nm) and green (λ 470 nm) filters under a fluorescence microscope (Eclipse Ts2, Nikon Instruments Inc., US).

2.11. Apoptosis-related messenger ribonucleic acid expression

Gene expression of B-cell lymphoma 2 (BCL2) and BCL2-associated X protein (BAX) and was assessed to investigate whether cell death was in response to an apoptotic stimulus according to Herbert [15]. Table 1 presents the primer sequences used for the quantitative analysis of apoptosis-related mRNA expression, including BAX, BCL2, and the endogenous control gene GAPDH. Cells (3 × 10⁵ cells mL⁻¹) were seeded in 6-well plates and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C, 5 % CO₂. Following treatments, ribonucleic acid (RNA) was isolated using Invitrogen TRIzol reagent according to the manufacturer's instructions. Specifically, the medium was removed and 400 µL of TRIzol reagent was added to each well prior to 5-minute incubation at ambient temperature. Then, 80 µL of chloroform was added to facilitate phase separation. This mixture was shaken to form an emulsion and incubated for 3 minutes at ambient temperature. Following centrifugation at 12000 ×g for 15 minutes at 4°C (Hettich Mikro 200 R), the aqueous phase containing the RNA was collected. For precipitation of the RNA, 200 µL of ice cold isopropanol was added and incubated for 10 minutes at ambient temperature. Following centrifugation at 12000 ×g for 10 minutes at 4°C, the supernatant was discarded, and the RNA pellet was washed with 400 µL of 75 % v/v ethanol. The RNA pellet was then centrifuged at 7500 ×g for 5 minutes at 4°C, after which the supernatant was discarded. The pellet was air-dried prior to resuspension in 20 µL of RNase-free water. RNA quality and concentration were determined using a DeNovix DS-11 spectrophotometer. A 260 nm/280 nm ratio of 1.8–2.0 was considered indicative of high RNA purity. Then, complementary deoxyribonucleic acid (cDNA) was synthesised from 200 ng of each RNA sample using the QuantiTech Reverse Transcription Kit (Qiagen) and subsequently amplified using the QuantiNova SYBR Green PCR Kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's instructions (Qiagen). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was conducted on the StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystem). PCR cycles were as follows: holding stage (95°C for 10 min), cycling stage (35 cycles: step 1, 95°C for 15 s; step 2, 60°C for 1 min), and melt curve stage (step 1, 95°C for 15 s; step 2, 60°C for 1 min; step 3, 95°C for 15 s). Relative expression was estimated using the 2^{-ΔΔCt} method. Values were expressed as mean ± SD of three

independent reactions.

2.12. Data treatment

Student's t-tests and one-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) were performed to determine significant differences among the microalgal trophic modes with respect to biomass yield, soluble protein content, and antioxidant capacity, as well as between cell culture treatments for viability, cytotoxicity and apoptosis-related mRNA expression. For the analyses, three independent biological replicates were used. For ANOVA, Tukey's post hoc test with a significance threshold of *p* = 0.05 was applied to identify significant differences within each group. All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 29 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Growth and biomass yields

T. chuii (CCAP 66/21B) exhibited contrasting growth rates when subjected to autotrophic and mixotrophic cultivation (Fig. 1A). Mixotrophy generated a higher cell density, reflected in the mean specific growth rate (0.055 ± 0.008 day⁻¹) compared to autotrophy (0.028 ± 0.017 day⁻¹). Furthermore, the mixotrophic growth regime also enhanced biomass yield (6-fold) compared to obligate autotrophic conditions (Fig. 1B).

3.2. Soluble protein content and antioxidant capacity

Fig. 2 (A) shows the soluble protein content of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) under autotrophic and mixotrophic conditions. Mixotrophy returned a significantly higher soluble protein yield (220.5 ± 24.3 mg BSA eq g⁻¹dw) compared to autotrophy (38.9 ± 5.9 mg BSA eq g⁻¹dw) (*p* < .001). This protein content accounted for 22.0 ± 2.4 and 3.9 ± 0.6 % of dry weight (DW) biomass, respectively. Fig. 2 (B) presents the antioxidant capacities of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) DPBS extracts under both conditions, assessed via DPPH free radical scavenging activity, Folin–Ciocalteu assay and the ABTS assay. In all cases, the antioxidant activity of extracts for the mixotrophic-derived *T. chuii* extracts was significantly higher compared to the autotrophic counterpart (Student *t* test, *p* < .001).

3.3. Cell viability

Fig. 3 shows the effects of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) DPBS extracts (24-hour treatment, 6.25–200 µg soluble protein mL⁻¹) on the viability of pulmonary carcinoma epithelial cells (A549). DPBS extracts derived from *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) under both autotrophic (Fig. 3A) and mixotrophic (Fig. 3B) cultivation modes had no significant effect on A549 cell viability across all tested concentrations. Viability remained comparable to the negative control, indicating no apparent cytotoxic or proliferative effects of *T. chuii*-derived DPBS extracts in this cellular context. In contrast, the positive controls, H₂O₂ (0.45 mM) and

Table 1

Primer Sequences for apoptosis-related mRNA expression. BAX and BCL2 expression was assessed to investigate whether cell death was in response to an apoptotic stimulus. Results were normalised to the endogenous control gene GAPDH.

Gene Name and Ascension Number	Primer Forward Sequence (5'-3')	Primer Reverse Sequence (5'-3')
GAPDH ¹ NM_002046	GTCTCTCTGACTTCAACAGCG	ACCACCGTGTGCTGTAGCCAA
BAX ² NM_004324	TCAGGATGCGTCCACCAAGAAG	TGTGTCCACGGCGGCAATCATC
BCL2 ² NM_000633	ATCGCCTGTGGATGACTGAGT	GCCAGGAGAAATCAACAGAGGC

References¹ [26],² [27].

Fig. 1. Growth profiles and biomass yields of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) for autotrophic and mixotrophic batch cultivation. **(A)** Optical density based (λ 600 nm) growth profiles. Absorbance measurements are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). **(B)** Biomass yields (mg mL^{-1}) of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) subjected to autotrophic and mixotrophic cultivation modes. Data in panel B refer to biomass collected on day 28 of cultivation. The letters a-b indicate groups in homogenous subsets, $p < .001$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$).

Fig. 2. Soluble protein content and antioxidant capacity of *T. chuii* DPBS extracts subjected to autotrophic and mixotrophic growth. **(A)** Soluble protein content ($\text{mg BSA eq g}^{-1}\text{dw}$) of DPBS extracts. The letters a-b indicate groups in homogenous subsets, $p < .001$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). **(B)** Antioxidant capacity ($\mu\text{mol trolox eq g}^{-1}\text{dw}$) of DPBS extracts: DPPH free radical scavenging assay, Folin-Ciocalteu assay and ABTS assay (trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity). The letters a-b indicate groups in homogenous subsets for each assay at $p < .001$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). Data in both panels refer to DPBS extracts obtained from biomass harvested on day 28 of cultivation.

doxorubicin ($2.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), significantly reduced viability to below 40 %.

Fig. 4 shows the dose-response effect of *T. chuii*-derived DPBS extracts against H_2O_2 -mediated cell death in A549 cells. For both autotrophic and mixotrophic-derived extracts (24-hour co-treatment with $0.45 \text{ mM H}_2\text{O}_2$), a cytoprotective effect was observed at $200 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$ with significantly improved viability ($p < .001$) compared to the H_2O_2 -only treatment ($0 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$). In contrast, lower extract concentrations ($6.25\text{--}25 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$) did not alleviate H_2O_2 -induced cytotoxicity and were associated with further reductions in cell viability ($p < .001$), suggesting that these doses may be insufficient to confer protection under oxidative stress conditions.

3.4. Cytotoxicity (lactate dehydrogenase assay)

Fig. 5 shows the protective effect of *T. chuii*-derived DPBS extracts against H_2O_2 -induced cytotoxicity in A549 cells. For both autotrophic and mixotrophic-derived extracts (24-hour co-treatment with $0.45 \text{ mM H}_2\text{O}_2$), a significant cytoprotective effect was observed at $200 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$ compared to the H_2O_2 -only treatment group ($0 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$) (autotrophic, $p = .002$; mixotrophic, $p < .001$). At lower concentrations ($6.25\text{--}100 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$), no significant

reduction in LDH release was observed compared to H_2O_2 -only treatments ($0 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$).

3.5. Acridine orange staining and epi-fluorescence

Acridine orange staining with epi-fluorescence microscopy was used to assess morphological changes and to identify apoptotic features in A549 cells treated with H_2O_2 alone or in combination with *T. chuii*-derived extracts. Viable cells exhibited bright green nuclei, early apoptotic cells displayed bright green condensed nuclei, and late apoptotic cells showed red nuclei with fragmented chromatin. Apoptotic features, such as nuclear fragmentation and red nuclei, were observed in all treatment groups (Fig. 6). For both autotrophic and mixotrophic-derived extracts ($200 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$), a 24-hour co-treatment with $0.45 \text{ mM H}_2\text{O}_2$ resulted in fewer apoptotic features and a higher proportion of viable cells (bright green nuclei) compared to the lower concentration treatments ($12.5 \mu\text{g soluble protein mL}^{-1}$) and the H_2O_2 -only treatment group. These findings suggest a potential cytoprotective effect of these extracts against oxidative stress-induced apoptosis in A549 cells.

Fig. 3. Effects of *T. chuui* DPBS extracts on A549 cell viability. **(A)** The effects of autotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extracts (24 h treatment) on A549 cell viability (percent of negative control). The letters a-b indicate groups in homogenous subsets, $p < .001$; $F = 190.7$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). **(B)** The effects of mixotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extracts (24 h treatment) on A549 cell viability (percent of negative control). The letters a-b indicate groups in homogenous subsets, $p < .001$; $F = 70.4$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). Data in both panels refer to DPBS extracts obtained from biomass harvested on day 28 of cultivation.

Fig. 4. Effects of *T. chuui* DPBS extracts on A549 cell viability co-treated with 0.45 mM H₂O₂. **(A)** The effects of autotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extracts on the viability of A549 cells co-treated with 0.45 mM H₂O₂ (24 h) (percent of negative control). The letters a-e indicate groups in homogenous subsets, $p < .001$; $F = 266.4$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). **(B)** The effects of mixotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extracts on the viability of A549 cells co-treated with 0.45 mM H₂O₂ (24 h) (percent of negative control). The letters a-f indicate groups in homogenous subsets, $p < .001$; $F = 469.6$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). Data in both panels refer to DPBS extracts obtained from biomass harvested on day 28 of cultivation.

Fig. 5. Effects of *T. chuii* DPBS extracts on A549 cytotoxicity after co-treatment with 0.45 mM H₂O₂. **(A)** The effects of autotrophic-derived *T. chuii* DPBS extracts on A549 cytotoxicity (LDH lysate percent of controls) after 24 h co-treatment with 0.45 mM H₂O₂. The letters a-f indicate groups in homogenous subsets, (ANOVA, $p < .001$; $F = 47.2$). All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). **(B)** The effects of mixotrophic-derived *T. chuii* DPBS extracts on A549 cytotoxicity (LDH lysate percent of controls) after 24 h co-treatment with and 0.45 mM H₂O₂. The letters a-e indicate groups in homogenous subsets, (ANOVA, $p < .001$; $F = 55.4$). All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). Data in both panels refer to DPBS extracts obtained from biomass harvested on day 28 of cultivation. The negative control corresponds to non-treated A549 cells, and the positive control is treatment with cell lysis solution (Abnova).

3.6. Apoptosis-related mRNA expression

Fig. 7 shows the relative mRNA expression of the apoptotic genes *BAX* and *BCL2*, normalised to *GAPDH* as the endogenous control. H₂O₂ treatment significantly increased *BAX* expression (3-fold) and decreased *BCL2* expression (2-fold) compared to the untreated control, consistent with oxidative stress-induced apoptosis. Co-treatment with *T. chuii*-derived DPBS extracts at 200 µg mL⁻¹ significantly reduced *BAX* expression and partially restored *BCL2* expression compared to H₂O₂ alone, indicating a potential cytoprotective effect. Furthermore, at lower concentrations (12.5 µg mL⁻¹), the autotrophic extract significantly increased *BAX* expression ($p < .001$) and reduced *BCL2* expression ($p < .001$), indicating a shift towards a pro-apoptotic gene expression profile at this dose. In contrast, the mixotrophic extract did not induce significant changes in these markers at the same concentration.

4. Discussion

4.1. Trophic mode: influence on biomass yield, soluble protein content and antioxidant capacity

Obligate heterotrophy and photoautotrophy are dependent on organic carbon assimilation and photosynthetic inorganic carbon fixation, respectively [28]. By contrast, facultative mixotrophy employs both heterotrophic and autotrophic metabolic pathways to negate the limitations caused by organic carbon depletion and photosynthetic dependency [29]. This metabolic flexibility facilitates sustained growth in mixotrophic regimes. Here, mixotrophy returned a significantly higher

growth rate and biomass yield compared to autotrophic conditions (Fig. 1), which is comparable to previous findings by Lu et al. [14]. Although prior studies on *T. chuii* have explored trophic modes primarily in the context of lipid accumulation for biofuel production [14], the present findings demonstrate that mixotrophic conditions not only enhance biomass yield but also influence the extractable protein content and antioxidant potential, indicating broader functional applications for this microalga. It has been shown that mixotrophy can also increase nitrogen assimilation, a process central to protein synthesis in microalgae [30,31]. Consistent with this, the present study demonstrated that mixotrophy returned a significantly higher soluble protein yield compared to autotrophy (Fig. 2). Additionally, studies have shown that mixotrophy upregulates antioxidant enzymatic activity (e.g., glutathione peroxidase and glutathione reductase) and the synthesis of heat shock proteins (e.g., Hsp70) as observed in the *Chlorella* genus [13,31, 32]. In mixotrophy, organic carbon assimilation disrupts conventional photosynthetic activity and promotes stress-related mechanisms and the formation of ROS [31,33]. Heat shock protein synthesis in microalgal cells may represent a strategy to regulate cellular redox imbalances through modulation of glutathione-related activities [32,34]. Supporting this, mixotrophic conditions significantly increased DPPH free radical scavenging activity and trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (ABTS and Folin-Ciocalteu assay) compared to autotrophic conditions (Fig. 2). In this context, polyphenols are known to form complexes with proteins [35]. Here, the amphiphilic properties of the surplus protein may act as a carrier for poorly soluble polyphenols (e.g., quercetin) [36, 37]. Thus, protein upregulation via mixotrophy may enhance protein-phenolic interactions, thereby improving the bioaccessibility and

Fig. 6. Representative acridine orange nucleic acid-selective fluorescence staining of A549 cells. (A) Untreated cells, (B) 0.45 mM H_2O_2 (24 h treatment), (C) autotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extract ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and 0.45 mM H_2O_2 (24 h co-treatment), (D) mixotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extract ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and 0.45 mM H_2O_2 (24 h co-treatment), (E) autotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extract ($12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and 0.45 mM H_2O_2 (24 h co-treatment), and (F) mixotrophic-derived *T.chuui* DPBS extract ($12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and 0.45 mM H_2O_2 (24 h co-treatment). Viable cells exhibit bright green nuclei; early apoptotic cells display bright green condensed nuclei; late apoptotic cells show red nuclei with fragmented chromatin. Extracts were obtained from biomass harvested on day 28 of cultivation. Representative images from three independent experiments. Magnification: $100\times$; Scale bar: $50 \mu\text{m}$.

solubility of polyphenolic compounds. This interaction between protein and polyphenols could, in turn, explain the observed upregulation in both protein content and antioxidant activity, as the increased protein content may facilitate the stabilization and solubilization of antioxidant-rich compounds, amplifying the overall bioactivity.

4.2. DPBS extraction and bioactivity: cytoprotective effects and cytotoxicity

Previous research on *Tetraselmis*-derived bioactive content has primarily focused on carotenoid-enriched solvent extracts and their restorative effects [15–17], in contrast to other extract types and their cytoprotective properties. Carotenoid pigments are primarily hydrophobic [38]. In contrast, the present study targeted, more polar bioactive constituents (e.g., hydrophilic phenolic and protein content) using a freeze-thaw-assisted DPBS extraction method [39]. This mild, non-denaturing extraction technique is known to preserve protein stability and can yield well resolved proteins of high to low molecular weight with minimal aggregation and precipitation [40]. To evaluate the cytoprotective bioactivity of these extracts, A549 cells were pre-exposed to the extracts for 1 hour prior to a co-treatment with H_2O_2

(0.45 mM) for a cumulative 24-hour treatment. Treatment with H_2O_2 alone reduced the viability of A549 cells relative to the negative control, which aligns with its established role in inducing oxidative stress, G1-phase arrest, and caspase-dependent apoptosis [41]. Co-treatment with DPBS extracts (normalised by soluble protein content) significantly increased the viability of H_2O_2 -stressed A549 cells, specifically at $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4). Additionally, reduced cytotoxicity was observed in the LDH assay (Fig. 5), which measures membrane integrity and serves as a valuable indicator of oxidative stress-induced cellular damage. The reduced LDH release in cells treated with high doses ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of *T. chuui* extracts suggests that the extracts may protect against oxidative stress-induced membrane damage, a hallmark of cellular injury during oxidative stress.

To justify the use of soluble protein content as a dosing metric in the bioactivity assays, the relationship between protein concentration and biological activity of the extracts was examined. A strong linear correlation was observed between protein-normalised extract concentration and A549 cell viability under H_2O_2 stress for both autotrophic and mixotrophic extracts, with Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.994 and 0.995, and corresponding R^2 values of 0.9887 and 0.9891, respectively (Supplementary Fig. S1). These findings support the use of soluble

Fig. 7. Effects of *T. chuii* DPBS extracts and 0.45 mM H₂O₂ co-treatment on mRNA expression. **(A)** The effects of *T. chuii* DPBS extracts and 0.45 mM H₂O₂ (24 h co-treatment) on *BAX* mRNA expression, normalised by *GAPDH*. *BAX* encodes for a protein that functions as an apoptotic activator. **(B)** The effects of *T. chuii* DPBS extracts and 0.45 mM H₂O₂ (24 h co-treatment) on *BCL2* mRNA expression, normalised by *GAPDH*. The apoptotic regulator *BCL2* encodes for a protein that blocks apoptotic cell death. The dotted line indicates the mRNA expression in the H₂O₂-only treatment group. Data in both panels refer to DPBS extracts obtained from biomass harvested on day 28 of cultivation. The letters a-d indicate groups in homogenous subsets, *BAX*, $p < .001$; $F = 59.7$; *BCL2*, $p < .001$; $F = 31.6$. All data are means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$).

protein as a reliable proxy for extract potency, reflecting a consistent association with antioxidant or cytoprotective effects across the dose range tested. Although proteins are unlikely to be the sole contributors to the observed bioactivity, the aqueous extraction conditions (DPBS) are known to co-extract a complex mixture of water-soluble compounds such as phenolics, peptides, and other small molecules, that may act synergistically to produce the biological effects observed. To further contextualise these findings, the antioxidant activity of the extract concentrations used in the cell-based assays were estimated based on TEAC values per µg protein (Supplementary Table S1). This increased antioxidant activity at higher protein concentrations would align with the enhanced protection against H₂O₂-induced cytotoxicity at 200 µg mL⁻¹.

Antioxidants such as flavonoids and carotenoids often exhibit concentration-dependent effects, acting as antioxidants at certain levels and potentially displaying pro-oxidant behavior under different redox conditions [42]. In this study, the biphasic dose-response pattern, characterised by pro-apoptotic effects at lower extract concentrations (<25 µg mL⁻¹) and cytoprotective effects at higher concentrations (200 µg mL⁻¹), could be interpreted in two ways. One possibility is a threshold effect, where low concentrations are simply insufficient to counteract H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress. Alternatively, the response may reflect a biphasic effect, as described by Jodynis-Liebert & Kujawska [43], where low and high doses elicit opposing effects. While both interpretations are plausible, the strong linear dose-response relationship observed in this study (Supplementary Fig. S1) suggests that the cytoprotective activity is more likely driven by a concentration-dependent effect than by a true non-monotonic biphasic mechanism.

4.3. Morphological changes and apoptosis-related mRNA expression

Programmed cell death (i.e., apoptosis) is the regulated self-destruction of damaged or non-functioning cells [44]. Apoptosis plays

a crucial role in maintaining cellular homeostasis, and its dysregulation is a key feature of many pulmonary diseases. Here, acridine orange staining with epi-fluorescence microscopy was used to assess the morphological features associated with apoptosis across the treatment groups (Fig. 6). Key apoptotic features, including nuclear fragmentation and chromatin condensation, were observed following exposure to H₂O₂. The high-dose co-treatment with *T. chuii* extracts (200 µg mL⁻¹) led to a reduction in these apoptotic features, suggesting a protective effect against oxidative stress-induced apoptosis. To further elucidate the molecular mechanisms, the expression of apoptosis-related genes (*BAX* and *BCL2*) was examined (Fig. 7). As expected, H₂O₂ treatment alone significantly upregulated the pro-apoptotic gene *BAX* and down-regulated the anti-apoptotic gene *BCL2*, which is consistent with the activation of the intrinsic apoptosis pathway [45]. The dose-dependent effects of the extracts was further reflected in the gene expression data. At low concentrations of the extract, there was potentiation of the pro-apoptotic effect, whereas high-dose co-treatment led to a reduction in *BAX* expression and partial restoration of *BCL2* expression, indicating cytoprotection. These findings indicate that *T. chuii* extracts modulate apoptosis-related gene expression in a dose-dependent manner, with lower concentrations insufficient to counteract apoptosis-related gene expression changes induced by H₂O₂, while higher concentrations were associated with a shift toward a more anti-apoptotic expression profile.

4.4. Mixotrophic cultivation to enhance antioxidant yields

In this study, mixotrophy significantly upregulated the bioactive content of *T. chuii* compared to obligate autotrophy (34.2-fold accounting for soluble protein yield and biomass generation). The differences observed between autotrophic and mixotrophic cultivation modes in terms of antioxidant activity can be attributed to variations in metabolic pathways. Consistent with our findings, Shetty & Sibi [46] reported that mixotrophic conditions enhanced the antioxidant potential of *Chlorella vulgaris*, likely due to the simultaneous utilisation of light

and organic carbon sources, which stimulate both photosynthetic and heterotrophic metabolism. Similarly, Bulut *et al.* [47] demonstrated that mixotrophic cultivation increased antioxidant activity in *Micractinium* sp., alongside elevated levels of total phenolics, flavonoids, and carotenoids. This enhanced antioxidant activity under mixotrophic conditions may be explained by the simultaneous activation of photosynthetic and respiratory pathways, which increases energy production and carbon flux, thereby upregulating secondary metabolite pathways such as those involved in phenolic biosynthesis. While mixotrophy supports higher growth rates and metabolite yields, its commercial-scale application remains limited due to the complexity of cultivation systems, high operational costs, challenges in using low-cost organic substrates, and increased risk of contamination. [48]. Addressing these issues is essential to enable effective scale-up, which could support the development of microalgae-derived antioxidant formulations with clinically relevant cytoprotective effects against oxidative stress, particularly for respiratory health, as well as broader applications in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and cosmetic industries where redox balance and cellular protection are key.

5. Conclusion

The present study highlights *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) as a valuable source of antioxidant bioactive compounds, with trophic mode playing a critical role in enhancing its bioactive content. Mixotrophy significantly upregulated key bioactive compounds compared to obligate photoautotrophy, showing notable increases in biomass yield (6.0-fold), soluble protein yield (5.7-fold) and Trolox-equivalent antioxidant capacity as measured by Folin-Ciocalteu (6.8-fold), DPPH (42.2-fold) and ABTS (15.3-fold) assays. Both autotrophic and mixotrophic-derived DPBS extracts of *T. chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) demonstrated dose-dependent effects in A549 cells exposed to H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress, with significant cytoprotection observed at higher concentrations (200 µg soluble protein mL⁻¹) and reduced viability at lower concentrations. These effects were accompanied by corresponding changes in apoptosis-related gene expression, including downregulation of *BAX* and partial restoration of *BCL2* at protective doses. While the mechanisms underlying these dose effects require further elucidation, including potential roles of ROS modulation and redox-sensitive signaling, the findings underscore the enhanced bioactivity associated with mixotrophic cultivation. Moreover, the findings highlight the potential of *T. chuii* extracts for applications targeting oxidative stress, particularly in pulmonary pharmacology, with broader relevance to pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries focused on redox homeostasis and cell protection.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thomas Conlon: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Helen Herbert:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Eva Campion:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Nicolas Touzet:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.procbio.2025.05.007.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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